

Combining CSR and Community Involvement for Covid-19 Crises Response

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Received : 05/01/2022

1st BPR : 12/01/2022

2nd BPR : 28/01/2022

Accepted : 10/02/2022

Abstract

The Pandemic highlighted the importance of community participation and corporate social responsibility during times of crisis. In march 2020 Government of India Announced the lockdown to fight against Covid-19 But lockdown is not the only way to fight against the COVID; the background of lockdown is community participation, and raising awareness about the pandemic in the community is very important. Community engagement is critical in the collective response to COVID-19, from complying with lockdown measures to taking steps as countries ease restrictions on community support through volunteering. Then here comes the importance of community participation and corporate social responsibility in COVID-19. This article if focused on role played by CSR for active community participation during COVID-19.

Key words: Community Participation, Corporate Social Responsibility, Covid-19, Health Well-Being.

Introduction

The unbreakable rule of the calendar is that the year ends on December 31st, and the new year begins with January 1st, but 2020 January is unlike any other, and the month brought the biggest pandemic of the last century, known as covid-19, which was completely unexpected by the world. When the World Health Organization declared COVID-19 a global pandemic, everyone tried to figure out what was going on in terms of the socioeconomic context of the pandemic, but no one found the correct picture of COVID-19, but everyone realized its results were very dire. In October 2020, the world cross the 40.2 million confirmed cases of the Covid-19. This number defined the covid-19 is long-lasting consequences for everyone, that movement world searching the sustainable way to tackle this Pandemic. The Pandemic highlighted the importance of community participation and corporate social responsibility during times of crisis. In march 2020 Government of India Announced the lockdown to fight against Covid-19 But lockdown is not the only way to fight against the COVID; the background of lockdown is community participation, and raising awareness about the pandemic in the community is very important. Community engagement is critical in the collective response to COVID-19, from complying with lockdown measures to taking steps as countries ease restrictions on community support through volunteering. Then here comes the importance of community participation and corporate social responsibility in COVID-19.

Community Participation

Community participation is the primary principle of community organization, which is the method of social work. The aim of community organization is to develop the capacity of the community by making it more organized so that it can handle its own needs or problems. The community participation tool can assist in achieving the expected results in the COVID-19 pandemic. The community participation principle of community organization helps to develop the economic, psychological, social, and health well-being of the community in the period of COVID-19. Community Participation/Engagement is it play important role to solved the problem because community know that which one is the best way or best solution of problem. Community engagement is critical in dealing with epidemics such as HIV, Ebola, Zika, and SARS, and COVID-19 is not unique, but it is dangerous compared to other epidemics.

Government take the step towards the participation of community because individual and collective responsibility matters to fight against the pandemic. The Government of India announced the lockdown and is requesting all citizens to support the lockdown and follow all regulations and safety precautions, etc. One side

government try to build the solidarity, trust, give moral support to Doctors and Para medical staff but second side authorities build the restriction but community except the restriction because community understand the need of restriction. The government body distributes food or rations to needy people at their door, raises awareness, and private organizations also contribute, but lack of planning and other factors contribute to the other side of lockdown or pandemic. When we discuss the dark side, many migrant workers walk on the road to save their lives and families, and many people lose their jobs in lockdown, according to one article of The Hindu An estimated 12.2 crore Indians lost their jobs during the coronavirus lockdown in April(Hindu 2020)

As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, the working class, business owners, industry, and trade have all suffered significant economic consequences. According to data from the Center for Monitoring the Indian Economy, the unemployment rate rose from 7.76% in February, a month before the Indian government imposed the lockdown, to 23.5% between March 26, 2020, and May 31, 2020. According to the data, job losses were more severe in occupations that require more interpersonal contact and cannot be performed remotely. Earning and maintaining a livelihood was particularly difficult in the informal employment sector such as tailors, traders and migrant workers. Job loss is also associated with significant psychological distress regarding the situation in the pandemic and the stress of finding a job in the future.

All of the problems were recognized by the community, but in that case, the community fought alongside the nation to defeat the covid-19. It is the most important aspect of community participation in the COVID-19 battle. Participation and engagement of the community are critical to achieving the desired outcome of Combat the pandemic

The Role Corporate Social Responsibility Plays During a Pandemic

In the time of COVID-19, corporate social responsibility plays an important role in achieving the desired outcomes against the pandemic. During the pandemic, when the country needed to fight COVID-19, CSR strongly supported the government, with many corporate companies donating to the PM Care Fund and many CSR organization's implementing their own policies to address the pandemic crisis

What is Corporate Social Responsibility?

The CSR organization plays an important role in building a better nation. CSR in the context of community development or community organization is not a new concept for India. When we talk about "give and take" or "giving back to the society," the process develops the concept of CSR from an Indian perspective. The CSR has a direct impact on the development or empowerment of marginalized, deprived, poor or underprivileged sections of the society.

CSR is a self-regulating business model that assists companies in being socially accountable to themselves, their stakeholders, and society at large. CSR It is a type of self-regulating international private business that aims to contribute to a philanthropic, charitable societal goal while supporting ethically oriented practice.

According to Archie Carroll, "The social responsibility of the business encompasses the economic, legal, ethical and discretionary that society has off originations at a given a point of time"

Constitutional Provisions of CSR in India

According to Section 135 of the Companies (CSR) Rules 2014 and Schedule VII of the Companies Act 2013, any company having a net worth of rupees five hundred core or more, a turnover of thousand core or more, or a net profit of five core or more During the company's immediate preceding financial year, it must have a corporate social responsibility committee and devote at least two percent of average net profits earned during the three immediate preceding financial years to its CSR policy.

Every company qualifying anyone norm then the company implement the CSR policy it is mandatory as per the section 135.

Importance of CSR

Survival businesses are no longer an economic unit that seeks only profit; instead, they thrive in societies where there is social justice, inequality, discrimination, and socio-ecological disparities. Here comes CSR, which is important for businesses to survive and be long lasting. CSR creates a balance between various direct and indirect stakeholders by requiring the company to act ethically. CSR focuses on long-term objectives and sustainable development rather than short-term economic goals. Environmental issues are the focus of CSR activities, which educate the corporation about its role in environmental prevention.

CSR in the period of Covid-19 Pandemic

The government's Ministry of Corporate Affairs has announced that any amount donated by companies for the fight against COVID-19 will qualify as CSR, with most companies either contributing to the PM Care Fund or for various other purposes, to protect the health and prevent starvation of the affected.

During COVID-19, the Indian government put pressure on companies to provide social assistance. According to a Ministry of Corporate Affairs circular dated March 23, 2020, all expenses incurred in connection with COVID-19 would be considered important forms of CSR spending. Another announcement made on May 5, 2020, in response to COVID-19 cases reaching four lacs per day, was that companies could use CSR funds to create health infrastructure for COVID-19 care, including the establishment of medical oxygen concentrators, ventilators, cylinders, and other medical equipment for countering COVID-19. The vast majority of Indian Company are actively involved in raising social distancing awareness in order to prevent the fatal epidemic from spreading. This is where the term corporate social responsibility comes into play, defining how a company communicates with its customers and citizens in order to create a socially responsible environment.

The CSR Funds are used for various activities related to COVID-19, Covered under the Schedule VII of the companies Act 2013:

1. Eradicating hunger
2. Poverty
3. Malnutrition
4. promoting healthcare, including preventive healthcare
5. Sanitation, including contribution to the Swachh Bharat Kosh set up by the Centre for promoting sanitation and making available safe drinking water
6. Disaster management, including relief, rehabilitation and reconstruction activities.

In following table shows the data regarding various development sector spent the amount through CSR activities in FY 2019-20 and FY 2020-21.

SECTORS	Fund Spent Financial Year 2019-20 (In Cr)	Fund Spent Financial Year 2020-21 (In Cr)	Difference in Funds Spent (In Cr)
Health Care	4902.69	7182.67	2279.98
Poverty, Eradicating Hunger, Malnutrition	1159.01	1380.27	221.26
Prime Minister'S National Relief Fund	797.13	1678.76	881.63
Safe Drinking Water	253.18	202.32	-50.86
Sanitation	521.72	335.45	-186.27
Swachh Bharat Kosh	53.42	160.85	107.43

When we analyse the amount spent by CSR during COVID-19 from financial year 2019-20 to financial year 2020-21 We discovered that more money is being spent on health care development, which has increased to 46.5%, while the Prime Minister's National Relief Fund has increased by 110.6%. The fund amount for eradicating poverty, hunger, and malnutrition increased by 19.09%, and the amount spent for Swachh Bharat Kosh increased by 201.1%, but the amount spent is comparatively less than in other sectors. Unfortunately, the amount spent in some sectors during the pandemic decreased for unknown reasons, with funds for safe drinking water falling by 20.08% and funds for sanitation falling by 35.70%. The only reason for the reduction in funding for these critical sectors is to assist the community and public sector in improving healthcare and to support the Prime Minister's National Relief Fund.

In the following section, we have highlighted a few examples of CSR Activities that have pioneered in fighting Covid-19

HCL Samuday is a rural flagship program of HCL Foundation. It is an outcome of HCL's commitment to uplift rural India. HCL Foundation is a CSR arm of HCL technologies. In the period of the pandemic, HCL Samuday worked on different areas, such as infrastructure, facility strengthening, equipment support for districts and frontline workers, Capacity building and technical support to district administration.

In the first phase HCL Samuday provided the integrated COVID Command Center with the Voice Infra Smartflo hybrid solution for the existing inbound and outbound calls and training on the usage of the Voice Infra solution to all the callers.

In the second phase, a software-based solution was developed in close collaboration with district administration to manage the entire patient/query load in the Hardoi district, as well as service delivery from various stakeholders, and software demonstration and batch-wise training on the software to the concerned team with consistent handholding support. Deployment of developed ICCC (Integrated Covid Command Center) software and scripts in the Hardoi Administration server. Further, HCL Foundation also supported the Branding of Covid Command Centre, and assets like laptops along with charger and bag, earphones and power extension boards (laptops along with charger and bag to be returned back from District Administration to HCL Foundation)

Standing firmly against the deadly Corona virus, HCL Samuday gears up to provide crucial on-the-ground support. HCL Samuday with district authorities, has set up an Integrated COVID Command Center (ICCC) in Hardoi, Uttar Pradesh.

Activating a tech-based automated system of call management, data was updated in real time. On-time calling records were observed on a single platform in the form of a dashboard, enabling efficient data management, follow-up, and reporting of all unconfirmed or suspected Covid cases.

Augmenting the COVID-19 testing facility, HCL Samuday modified two mobile COVID-19 testing vehicles with the collaborations of district administration that facilitated the screening of 55032 people. Samuday established three Covid screening Booths operational by Govt. staff at 3 Community Health Centres in Hardoi district.

HCL Samuday provided PPE kits (Personal Protective Equipment), 2 state-of-the-art thermal imaging units, a 100-degree infrared thermometer, and 10 oxygen concentrators (ultramodern O2 concentrators) for supporting COVID critical care, as well as the pulse oximeters to effectively monitor blood oxygen saturation in COVID individuals for district workers treating COVID patients. HCL Foundation established the two PSA (Pressure Swing Adsorption) oxygen plants for effective and comprehensive COVID care at CHC Sandila and District Hospital Hardoi and installed a CCTV COVID patient surveillance system for a 100-bed Level-2 COVID facility in Hardoi.

Tata Motors, as part of its CSR initiative, is focused on supplying essential items to communities most affected by the COVID-19 lockdown by facilitating the production of protective equipment and medical kits to prevent the spread of COVID-19. So far, the company has provided more than 25,000 cooked food packages and more than 5,000 grocery kits (rations) to migrants and homeless communities, urban slum dwellers, drivers, co-drivers, mechanics, temporary and contract workers. In addition, the company has established two food helpline numbers for temporary and contract workers in Lucknow and is providing water to 19 police stations and traffic police in Pune. Tata Motors has also collaborated with Indian Oil Corporation to provide food parcels and personal protection kits to truck drivers visiting "Saarthi Aaram Kendra (SAK)" in Narsapura (near Bengaluru) and Bawal (near Gurugram). In addition, the company is helping and supporting self-help groups to make certified homemade masks and sanitizers for distribution to hospitals, vendors, healthcare

workers, police stations, military personnel, and communities around company plants. The company has allowed the manufacture of 17,000 certified homemade masks and has also facilitated the distribution of N95 masks, disinfectants and personal protective equipment kits that are distributed to municipal hospitals. In addition, it conducted medical checkups and provided basic medicines to more than 500 truckers and co-drivers stranded at Belur in Dharwad.

The Adani Foundation, the Adani Group's philanthropic arm, has contributed Rs 100 crore to the PM CARES Fund to combat the Corona virus pandemic. The group donated Rs. 5 crore and Rs. 1 crore to Gujarat and Maharashtra CM relief funds, respectively. Given the changing situation surrounding the spread of COVID-19 in communities.

Reliance Foundation has donated Rs 5 crore to the Telangana Chief Minister's Relief Fund (CMRF) to support the state's COVID-19 relief efforts. RIL and Reliance Foundation have also contributed over Rs 530 crore to PM-CARES and other relief funds. In collaboration with BMC, Sir HN Reliance Foundation Hospital set up a dedicated 100-bed facility, which will now be expanded to 250 beds at Seven Hills Hospital in Mumbai, Maharashtra. Mukesh Ambani-led Reliance Foundation has pledged to provide meals worth Rs 3 crore to marginalized communities and frontline workers across the country through Reliance Foundation. The food will be provided through 'Mission Anna Seva', which will be the world's largest food distribution program run by a corporate foundation. The Reliance Foundation manufactured one lakh of masks and one lakh of personal protective equipment (PPE) daily for health workers and caregivers. Reliance also provides free fuel to emergency vehicles and Reliance Retail delivers essential supplies to more than 200 cities every day.

Essar Foundation is living up to Essar's ethos of "creating value" during the unprecedented crisis posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic of COVID-19. The Essar Foundation is doing everything they can to help their communities combat the crisis, whether it's partnering with local government bodies or NGOs, fundraising, or providing food and medical supplies. Through the District Collector's Office in Mumbai, the Essar Foundation provides two meals per day to over 1000 migrant workers in Kalbadevi for one month. In collaboration with Pragati Holistic Development Trust, we provide monthly groceries to 1000 families in Dharavi (including 70 transgender people and 75 senior citizens). A month's worth of food and dry rations were distributed to Mumbai's 675 slum dwellers (135 families).

Essar Foundation support for health workers and police officers , Food for a month for slum dwellers on Cuffe Parade through the Bhaker Foundation and Migration food for over 1000 doctors for a month in collaboration with Project Mumbai, Doctors in Bhabha 100 protective gear (PPE suits) for Municipal Hospital, Mumbai, Aundh Chest Hospital, Pune, 40,000 3-ply masks for frontline healthcare workers, government hospitals (KEM, JJ, Nair, Sion and Wadia), Haffkine Institute and Mumbai Police Assistance in providing preventive protective equipment (PPE) to Suits, N95 masks, 3-ply masks and insurance for contract workers, as well as supplies such as a clothing line, masks, sanitizers and sanitizers.

Essar Foundation's support to women and transgender communities: Menstruation with Dignity campaign: 1000 packs of sanitary napkins sourced from Myna Mahila Foundation, a women-centric micro-enterprise, and distributed by field partners to slum communities in Mumbai: YUVA.

URJA Trust, a shelter for women laboring in battered environments and domestic violence, has received essential items such as sanitary napkins, handwashing packets, antiseptic liquids, soaps and detergents, which ensures coverage for one month of lockdown.

The Rainbow Initiative", a transgender awareness initiative run by the Essar Foundation, involves rescue efforts, financial assistance and provision of food and essential items for members of the transgender community in India [Noida (Delhi), Dharavi (Mumbai) and Thotukudi. , Tamil Nadu]; There is intense coordination with Joint Working Groups for Trans People to strengthen structured relief efforts.

A Call for 'Personal Social Responsibility' from the Essar COVID-19 Relief Fund the Essar COVID-19 Relief Fund contribution campaign has been launched to give ESSAR employees the opportunity to contribute monetary contributions to the ESSAR Foundation's COVID-19 relief efforts. The Fund is also being expanded externally, with other corporations joining forces to form a syndicated fund to provide relief to our communities' most marginalized, vulnerable, and neglected groups. (the data collected at FCCI)

Conclusion

The article findings indicated the study of CSR and Community contribution during covid-19. The pandemic is not only Public health crisis it is also socio economic crisis for entire world. When we analyzed the data of CSR

Expenditure during covid-19 it justifies the importance of CSR, How CSR played a crucial role during crisis time. CSR provides a way to maintain consumer confidence, investor confidence and workforce loyalty. If there is one simple lesson to be learned, it is that CSR practices can be effective in responding to a crisis/pandemic period. CSR has the potential to foster the community participation and the informal sector in social activities, as well as in national development. It can serve to help the community to recognize and act on its fundamental duties, thus educating the population on the importance of being a responsible community during crisis. The article shows the demonstration of community engagement initiative based on the principles of community organization, social work methodology can help to achieve desired outcomes and improve the well-being of the participants. The success of such tools in pandemic situations gives hope that they can be successfully transferred to the post-COVID era if woven with similar intentions. Finally, it can be concluded that the mixture of CSR and community involvement can be effective socio-economic tool in the moments of crisis.

References

1. *A Community Participation Initiative During COVID-19 Pandemic: A Case Study From India*. (2021, February 19). Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine. <https://journals.sagepub.com/>
2. Bhatnagar, A., & Arora, A. (2021, August 8). *CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC: RESPONSE OF SELECT INDIAN COMPANIES*. ijert.org.
3. *Corporate social responsibility practices in the times of COVID-19: A study of India's BFSI sector : Banking, finance and insurance firms must understand the areas in which the society needs action and focus on them*. (2020, December 10). <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/>. <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/blog/governance/corporate-social-responsibility-practices-in-the-times-of-covid-19-a-study-of-india-s-bfsi-sector-74583>
4. *Data | An estimated 12.2 crore Indians lost their jobs during the coronavirus lockdown in April: CMIE: More than 3/4th of those who lost jobs are wage labourers and small traders; Tamil Nadu is among the worst hit States*. (2020, May 7). THE HINDU.
5. *FICCI Members Contribution towards fight against COVID-19*. (n.d.). FICCI. https://ficci.in/sector/report/20588/COVID-19_Intervention.pdf
6. Ganeshan, M. K., [Ph.D Full-time Research Scholar, Department of Alagappa Institute of Management School of Management, Alagappa University, Karaikudi], & Vethirajan, C., [Professor & Head, Department of Corporate Secretaryship School of Management, Alagappa University, Karaikudi]. (n.d.). *THE ROLE OF INDIAN COMPANIES TOWARDS CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC*.
7. Koli, A., & Mehta, R. (2020, December 10). *Corporate social responsibility practices in the times of COVID-19: A study of India's BFSI sector Archana Koli, Rutvi Mehta : Banking, finance and insurance firms must understand the areas in which the society needs action and focus on them*. <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/>. <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/blog/governance/corporate-social-responsibility-practices-in-the-times-of-covid-19-a-study-of-india-s-bfsi-sector-74583>
8. Kolli, S. K., & Srikanth, A. (2020, August). *The Participation Of Indian Firms During Covid-19 Pandemic- A Corporate Social Responsibility Perspective*. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. https://ejmcm.com/article_4550_dab714214bf8af3ccc34143ccedfc0e5.pdf
9. *Ministry of corporate affairs- National CSR Portal*. (n.d.). <https://www.csr.gov.in/content/csr/global/master/home/ExploreCsrData/company-wise.html>
10. Oluwatemiloro Adenipekun. (n.d.). *COVID-19—A Review of Community Participation : Citizen participation can reduce damages caused by the pandemic and—crucially—help identify a sustainable path forward*. Think Global Health.
11. *REPORT OF THE HIGH LEVEL COMMITTEE ON CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY 2018: Government of India Ministry of Corporate Affairs August, 2019*. (2019, August 7). <https://www.mca.gov.in/>.
12. The Hindu, 2020, <https://www.thehindu.com/data/data-over-12-crore-indians-lost-their-jobs-during-the-coronavirus-lockdown-in-april/article61660110.ece>

